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Maftuna Ibodullayeva HabibullayevnaTeacher at the Samarkand State
Institute of Foreign Languages**TEACHING INTERACTIVE WAYS OF CONDUCTING RESEARCH TO THE
STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7680041>**ANNOTATION**

This article discusses some interactive ways of teaching researching to students of Higher Education. The ways of encouraging students to do their research works have been explained with examples taken from research writing classes. The background of the problem and findings of other scholars were studied and discussed. With the help of conducted experiments and taken questionnaires some results have been taken and methods and techniques of teaching researching have been proven to be useful. This paper suggests a sound, practical approach for writing up a research project for teaching beginner-researcher students.

Key words: research, teaching researching, choosing an interesting topic, topic narrowing skills, inside-out approach, outside-in approach, experiments

Maftuna Ibodullayeva Habibullayevna

Samarqand davlat chet tillar instituti o'qituvchisi

**OLIV TA'LIM TALABALARIGA TADQIQOT O'TKAZISHNING INTERFAOL
USULLARINI O'RGATISH****ANNOTATSIYA**

Ushbu maqolada oliy ta'lim talabalariga tadqiqot olib borishning ba'zi interaktiv usullari muhokama qilinadi. Talabalarni tadqiqot ishlarini bajarishga undash yo'llari tadqiqot yozish darslaridan olingan misollar bilan tushuntirildi. Muammoning kelib chiqishi va boshqa olimlarning xulosalari o'rganildi va muhokama qilindi. O'tkazilgan tajribalar va olingan so'rovnomalar yordamida ma'lum natijalar olindi, tadqiqot o'rgatishning metod va usullari foydali ekanligi isbotlandi. Ushbu maqola boshlang'ich-tadqiqotchi talabalarni o'rgatish uchun tadqiqot loyihasini yozish uchun ishonchli va amaliy yondashuvni taklif qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: tadqiqot, o'rgatish va o'rganish tadqiqoti, sarlavha tanlash, qiziqarli ilmiy tadqiqot mavzusi, mavzuni toraytirish ko'nikmalari, ichkaridan tashqariga yondashuv, tashqaridan ichkariga yondashish, tajribalar

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ПРЕПОДАВАНИЕ ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫХ СПОСОБОВ ПРОВЕДЕНИЯ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ СТУДЕНТАМ ВУЗОВ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье рассматриваются некоторые интерактивные способы обучения исследовательской деятельности студентов высших учебных заведений. Способы стимулирования студентов к выполнению своих исследовательских работ были объяснены на примерах, взятых из курсов по научно-исследовательской работе. Были изучены и обсуждены предыстория проблемы и выводы других ученых. С помощью проведенных экспериментов и анкет были получены некоторые результаты и доказана эффективность методов и приемов обучения исследованию. В этой статье предлагается надежный практический подход к написанию исследовательского проекта для обучения начинающих исследователей.

Ключевые слова: исследование, обучение исследованию, выбор интересной темы для научной работы, навыки сужения темы, подход «изнутри наружу», подход «снаружи внутрь», эксперименты.

“Good scientists study the most important problems they think they can solve. It is, after all, their professional business to solve problems not to grapple with them.”

Peter Medawae

Introduction

In this fast-paced process of globalization, one highly demanded skill from professional personnel is scientific skill and aptitude. This important skill should be taught beginning at school and should be practiced as a must-have skill at higher educational institutions. This process follows several thoroughly planned steps and the process itself should be carried out by highly competitive scientific researchers or teachers. In most developed countries over the world special attention is paid to the direction of students to research activities; scholars direct students to research activities, identifying gifted students and directing them to their preferred fields. Concerning the development of researching process, lots of significant decrees have been signed, one of them is the Decree of the PF 5712 of October 8, 2019, «The Concept of Development of Higher Education in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030» [1]. Researching means the increase of critical thinking skills of learners, it means more independent and initiative students.

Researching is a gradual process of advancing one's knowledge of any chosen sphere or in other words, contributing a piecemeal increase to any field. There are several definitions and expressions to describe the notion 'research' and many ways can be found to teach how to do it. The world of research is famous for being full of factual, experimental and time-consuming instances. Actuality plays a significant role in research conducting process, what is more, novelty perhaps precedes above stated feature in many cases. Creating something new and obtaining worthy results may only come with well-planned research steps and methods. With no doubt, all these criteria make researching process not only arduous, but they also promise your work be reliable and valid.

There are a lot of ways of organizing research papers, one of them is so-called IMRaD. However, as a guide for someone writing up research data for the first time, it is far from complete for example, there is no detailed abbreviation like T for title or even S for summary. Nor does IMRaD explain what belongs in which section and how much should be included in or excluded from any section. Everything should be explained and shown in samples written in this style. As a supplement to, but not a replacement for, IMRaD research-workers could bear in mind the six honest serving-men of the poet Rudyard Kipling [12]. These writer's mind-map is called What, Why, When, How, Where, and Who, and they can be applied to all parts of the paper from its title down to the tables.

These kinds of researching may help to organize original articles, case reports, technical notes, pictorial essays, reviews, commentaries and editorials. Authors should be aware that each type of paper is specific in nature, serve a distinct purpose, and is judged by different criteria. [3]

Nurturing and educating real research loving generation is not that as tough as majority of us think, yet it is not easy as well. One of the most important factors of this process is instilling main

necessities of researching in the mind of learners. Initially, doing research may seem to be odd, futile or complicated process for beginner students. They might not comprehend the initiatives of researching or probably could not find any benefit of doing it. However, as language learner students they may gain long-term massive boons for their skill enriching process. The barriers addressed are time, failure to recognize expertise, a reluctance to subject one's work and ideas to the public arena for scrutiny, and lack of confidence with scholarly writing. [8]

The purpose of this study is to share gained experience in research skills teaching sphere and spread some interactive methods of triggering interest of students of higher education to research.

Materials and Methods

In order to bring researchers' interests to the surface, an approach called "inside-out" can be used for better productivity. This approach was coined by S. Covey [4] in his book and the use of this approach is slightly different in this situation. Benefits are chosen for personal improvement of students (inside-out), not for the sake of others (outside-in approach). There, we found some minimum benefits of doing research for language learner students:

1. Vocabulary or language skills boost
2. Advancement of knowledge in one sphere
3. Widening their horizon

These three benefits have not stated about main requirements of researching process yet, but they are enough to encourage learners' motives to do a little research at least. Any language learners want to be fluent and they want to be better in their sphere. While researching, they unconsciously will have to study new set of vocabulary, simultaneously they improve their reading and writing skills. These pros of researching are for the first benefit in the above given list. For the second, students increase their knowledge generally, it naturally happens in researching process. Thirdly, they become more perceptive, thorough and critical to choose information, all of these serve to widen their horizon improving their insights. Overall, this step was only to help beginner researchers to commence their first steps in research world. Furthermore, as Jane E. Mills [7] stated one of the most supportive factors of researching is financial rewards for researchers for an article to minimum. The approach outside-in is about the benefit of research results to society or to one group of people.

Quite different steps to carry out research are recommended by different scientists and researchers. As a teacher or a guide to instruct students for researching, one should set his own research map with learners. Not only does it help teachers and learners understand and know what to do in each step, but also mind-mapping process assists researchers to ease research process in advance. Mostly topics are presented researchers without giving the choice to choose; still, for better productivity, honesty, reliability and advancement in researching world, set of topics should be given at the disposal of researchers. There is a difference between 'title' and topic. Topic is a wide term that may consist of several titles or subtopics, while title or subtopic should be narrow and approachable. In most cases, given or chosen topics are not interesting or not updated. Therefore, it is mostly advised to choose a topic according to these criteria:

- title should be interesting to the researcher
- it should be current
- it should be pertinent to researcher's major

In the experiment conducted with the fourth and second course students of SSIFL (Samarkand State Institute of foreign languages), we have narrowed several general topics together in research writing classes. To make the process easier they were given 10 social topics and they narrowed their chosen topics in pair, with their research partners.

Subsequently, if the topic is meeting all the above given requirements, it is absolutely normal and not difficult for researchers. If the topic is too wide, it is likely to be tough to get results from experiments. Even compiling theoretical part of research paper possibly becomes confusing and less productive, since most spheres have been studied by scholars owing to swift advancement of science. There are a few ways of narrowing the topic, setting questions is one of the most effective ways of it. To be sure for making research paper resultful and intriguing, each researcher should ask title these three questions: When? Where? Who?

If we see our little rule in examples that were done by students in the topic narrowing experiment, one of the students was given a topic “Relationships”. Answering to the questions stated above, researcher chose a title like this: “The relationship between mothers-in-law and student daughters-in-laws in Samarkand”. As one can see, the title is answering all the questions, when? – it is certain that time is current, who? - mothers-in-law and student daughters-in-laws, where? - Samarkand. Identifying a title in this way helps researcher to work easily, especially if the researcher lives in chosen place. Another beneficial factor of this narrowing activity is increase in students’ attention and interest, then they see and understand that researching is no more impossible to do. Approximately 60% -80% of learners at the institute are newly married female students. In each class 7 or 8 students from 15 are fascinated with the chosen and narrowed title.

In this way we could trigger majority of ignorant students to research. Plus, it is believed that with these specific topics results will be more reliable, because it is difficult for the researcher to copy someone’s results, plagiarism is avoided, as well. Another student-researcher pair chose topic “Crime” and they narrowed it to “The causes and consequences of high increase of crime among students of universities in Uzbekistan”

While refining title, researcher should take into account that resources must be available on the internet, in the library or researchers should be able to find them in soft or hard copies from any approachable source. Students think that they will not come up with their own ideas while writing their research paper; however, they should be convinced that they unconsciously begin thinking critically and thoroughly after studying a few materials at least. Printed versions of literature are preferable for convenience.

Another important part of teaching how to conduct research is a wise preparation for experiment part. Every researcher should plan and prepare well in order to get deserving results and have an effective methodology. Set of questions for interview or focus groups should be well-developed by students consulting their supervisors. Gender, age, locus, occupation and likewise personal indicators should be taken into consideration for better and different results.

As students’ major is specific for qualitative research traits, they used literature review method where they compared and contrasted the opinions of other scholars who worked before them [10]. Another frequent research methods used by students was questionnaire one-to-one interview methods, since they considered these methods time-efficient, budget-efficient and less complicated one. During the experiments, young researchers wholeheartedly enjoyed the process and enthusiastically analyzed and grouped the gathered data.

Analyzing and synthesizing process was the most difficult step for majority of the students, because they were confused to pick right information from gathered materials. Teacher assisted in this process advising students to think more critically and logically.

During a 10-pair subject called “Research writing”, students drew their research design or plan that consisted of 8 specific steps. We will define general peculiarities of each step described in brackets, it was quite easy to follow the steps as all steps was shown firstly in sample works by the teacher. They are followings:

- I. Choose a topic (identify your title with your supervisor using narrowing activities)
- II. Literature review (students gathered at least 5 articles, books or materials, they divided them into primary and secondary resources)
- III. Raise questions and identify gaps or problems of the given topic (students set their questions to which they followed while they were setting their hypothesis)
- IV. Set hypothesis (students learned types of hypothesis, set their hypothesis to the questions they raised)
- V. Make up your outline (blueprint) and plan (students understood the difference between outline and plan)
- VI. Analyzing and synthesizing process (collected literature was studied thoroughly and all taken information was grouped, experiment, questionnaire, surveys were conducted)
- VII. Compile your research paper (students took necessary information from resources to compose their paper)

VIII. Presentation or interpretation part (students presented, published their completed works)

Following all these steps, beginner researchers presented their finished papers in the 10th lesson to the teacher, they shared their experience and knowledge with one another.

Results

During the research period more than 100 articles in IMRAD style were gathered by students; from 45 students 22 students published their articles to local and republican conference journals; 18 of the published articles were written by co-authors, 4 of them were published by individual authors, 13 students presented their research paper in the form of mega-essay with about 1-2,5 pages, 5 students presented their work in the form of power point presentation, 5 students failed. According to the answers of the students in the questionnaire, 80% of all students admitted and confessed about their gained knowledge of researching and as they stated they developed their scientific writing skills as well. The students who failed in this process might not succeed because of ignorance, low language level and perhaps less attention of the instructor.

Students	Subject	Language level (approximate percentages)	Students with developed research writing skills	Published articles	Research paper in the form essay	Research presentation in the form power point presentation
2 nd course	Theoretical base of research writing	8-10% - C 1 50% - B2 25% - B1 15% - lower than B1	60% - 70%	6	7	2
4 th course	Research writing	20% - C 1 55% - B2 25% - B1 5-7% - lower than B1	70% - 80%	12	6	3

All of the numbers shown in the table are calculated approximately according to the answers for questionnaires, participation and oral interviews of students.

Discussion

The data analysis reveals that there is a considerable difference between the result of published articles of 2nd and 4th course students. This is considered that first important factor of high numbers of published articles is that majority of graduates are given diploma works, graduation papers. As a result, they had already been somehow aware of researching process, while sophomore students stepped into the research world for the first time. Meanwhile, all students in the groups showed different interests towards classes and instructions of the teacher. Although an internationally accepted style – IMRAD explained in detail several times, some of the students preferred to present their research paper in essay form, the result is nearly equal with slight high amount of second course students.

There may be other external factors for these results as well. Some researchers presented their works in the forms of electronic presentation, they took videos of some interviews and demonstrated their results in pictures, but as it is shown in the table, they are only 5. Language barriers were often considered as major problems to understand the collected literature, translating all the answers or respondents was also time-consuming. Students had challenges in setting questions and preparing for experiment part because of less experience. Helping them with samples taken from real experiment was a light led to their successful

Observations, interviews, interviews and like these research methods show that in the current research work, the majority of young researchers are inadequate use of information technology,

inadequate competence to conduct research, the inability to write scientific articles, and the lack of creative writing skills.

Conclusion

To summarize, ways of researching can be taught interactively and productively with real samples taken research papers. Students can be easily made to be interested in research world, where there is research, there is a development. Our world needs this development, especially young generation must do a lot of dig-up work. It is important to mention that all efforts are made to ensure that the students develop these vital scientific writing skills [13]. The replication of this kind of research is being planned to conduct with other course and group students to increase their awareness and interest to researching. It is the second time we have done a little research study to check the interest of learners in higher education to researching. When the results of the research were demonstrated to the learners, they expressed their astonishment and they said that they never expected this.

Whatever is done in research field only serves for the better improvement of different fields. As stated above, it benefits the researcher firstly, secondly it brings gradual development for the society. Researching provides the activation of the intellectual activity of the student, the independent acquisition of knowledge, the development of creative abilities, the development of professional skills, the formation of the professionalism of the future specialist. These kinds of research done by teachers should be carried out timely for the better results in research field, for high increase in the number of research works.

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СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

6 ЖИЛД, 1 СОН

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

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